

POTENTIAL CLINICAL RELEVANCE OF THE COMMON PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL PATHWAY IN KOUNIS SYNDROME AND NON ALLERGIC ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT Kounis syndrome is an acute coronary syndrome associated with mast cell and platelet activation in the setting of allergic or anaphylactic reactions. The mediators released from the same inflammatory cells are also present in acute coronary events of a non-allergic aetiology. Therefore, there is a piece of sufficient evidence of a common pathophysiological pathway between allergic and non-allergic acute coronary syndrome, with mast cells and proinflammatory molecules such as histamine, tryptase, chymase, thromboxane, leukotrienes, and IL-6, playing a crucial role. On the other hand, there is no sufficient evidence to support the use of intravenous corticosteroids and/or antihistamines in non-allergic acute coronary syndrome, but further clinical research might be relevant.

KEYWORDS Kounis syndrome, corticosteroids, pathophysiology

To the Editors, Kounis syndrome, defined as the occurrence of an acute coronary syndrome associated with mast cell and platelet activation in the setting of allergic or anaphylactic reactions, has three types: coronary vasospasm (type I, allergic angina), native plaque destabilization (type II, allergic myocardial infarction) and stent thrombosis (type III)[1]. Kounis Nicholas hypothesized in his article that Kounis syndrome represents a magnificent natural paradigm and nature's own experiment in a final trigger pathway implicated in cases of coronary artery spasm and plaque rupture. The same mediators released from the same inflammatory cells are also present in acute coronary events of non allergic etiology, which are not only present in the culprit region before plaque erosion or rupture but also release their contents just before an actual coronary event. Increased histamine levels, increased serum tryptase and chymase levels, increased levels of arachidonic acid products (including thromboxane and leukotrienes), and increased interleukin-6 levels, were also found in patients suffering from the non-allergic

acute coronary syndrome, which means that there is a common pathophysiological pathway in both Kounis syndrome and non-allergic acute coronary syndrome. It is well known that treating allergic events alone (intravenous corticosteroids, H1 and H2 antihistamines) can abolish symptoms in type I Kounis syndrome. In patients with allergic myocardial infarction (type II), treatment consists of an acute coronary event protocol and an anti-allergy protocol (corticosteroids, antihistamines). In type III Kounis syndrome, treatment consists of acute myocardial infarction protocol, urgent aspiration of intra-stent thrombus and anti-allergy protocol[2]. Considering that there is a common pathophysiological pathway in allergic and non-allergic acute coronary syndrome, it is plausible to hypothesise that anti-allergy protocol could be beneficial in treating non-allergic acute coronary syndrome and that early implementation of such protocol could prevent or mitigate myocardial damage. A study designed to investigate the potential interplay between corticosteroid treatment and in-hospital myocardial infarction in adults with community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) showed that in-hospital corticosteroid treatment was associated with a lower incidence of myocardial infarction in adults hospitalized with CAP (hazard ratio, 0.46; 95% CI, 0.24 to 0.88; P=0.02)[3]. A meta-analysis of corticosteroid treatment in acute myocardial infarction in 2003 demonstrated no harm and a possible mortality

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benefit of corticosteroids in acute myocardial infarction[4].

While there is a piece of sufficient evidence about the common pathophysiological pathway between allergic and nonallergic acute coronary syndrome, with mast cells and pro-inflammatory molecules such as histamine, tryptase, chymase, thromboxane, leukotrienes, and IL-6, playing a crucial role, there is no sufficient evidence to support the use of intravenous corticosteroids and/or antihistamines in a non-allergic acute coronary syndrome, but further clinical research on this issue might be relevant. In addition, early intravenous corticosteroid administration in a patient presenting with symptoms and signs of the acute coronary syndrome might be useful, but more research is necessary.

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Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the authors of this study.

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